

OXIRGI RAQAMI 6, 7 VA 8 BO‘LGAN SONLARNING KVADRATINI HISOBLASH FORMULALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktabi o‘quvchilari hamda Oliy ta’lim muassasalari talabalari uchun oxirgi raqami 6, 7 va 8 raqamlaridan iborat bo‘lgan sonlarning kvadratini hisoblovchi umumiy formula keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Oxirgi raqami 6, 7 va 8 bilan tugovchi sonlarning kvadratini hisoblash uchun formula.

FORMULAS FOR CALCULATING THE SQUARE OF NUMBERS WITH THE LAST NUMBER 6, 7 AND 8

Annotation: This article provides a formula for calculating the squares of numbers ending in 6, 7 and 8, which can be used by students of secondary schools, as well as students of higher educational institutions.

Keyword: Formula for calculating the square of numbers ending in 6, 7 and 8.

Umumiy o‘rta ta’lim maktab Matematika fani kursidan ma’lumki, oxirgi raqami 5 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonning kvadratini hisoblash formulasi mavjud.

$$\overline{a5} \square \overline{a5} = \overline{(a+1) \square a5} \quad (1)$$

Ammo, oxirgi raqami 6, 7 va 8 raqamlari bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonning kvadratini hisoblashning umumiy formulasi ustida uncha ko‘p ishlar amalga

oshirilmaganligi barchamizga ayondir. Ushbu masalaga javobni misollar orqali qidirish zarur deb hisoblayman.

Oxirgi raqami 6 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonni o'ziga o'zini ko'paytirish natijasida hosil bo'ladigan sonlarni topishning umumiy formulasi:

$$\overline{a6} \overline{a6} = a(a+1)(2a+3)6 \quad (2)$$

Misol uchun: oxirgi raqami 6 ning kvadratini ushbu formula orqali hisoblaymiz.

Bunda, $a=0$ qo'yib tekshirsak.

$$a = 0$$

$$66 = 36$$

$$a = 0$$

$$0(0+1)(2 \cdot 0 + 3)6 = (0)(3)6 = 36$$

O'nlar sinfini misol sifatida tekshirsak:

$$a = 5$$

$$5656 = 3136$$

$$a = 5$$

$$5(5+1)(2 \cdot 5 + 3)6 = (30)(13)6 = (30+1)16 = 3136$$

Yuzlar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 18$$

$$186186 = 34596$$

$$a = 18$$

$$18(18+1)(2 \cdot 18 + 3)6 = (342)(39)6 = (342+3)96 = 34596$$

$$a = 865$$

$$86568656 = 74926336$$

Minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 865$$

$$865(865+1)(2 \cdot 865 + 3)6 = (749090)(1733)6 = \\ = (749090+173)36 = 74926336$$

O'n minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 2579$$

$$25796 \square 25796 = 665433616$$

$$a = 2579$$

$$2579 \square (2579 + 1)(2579 \square 2 + 3)6 = (6653820)(5161)6 = \\ = (6653820 + 516)16 = 665433616$$

Yuz minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 25198$$

$$251986 \square 251986 = 63496944196$$

$$a = 25198$$

$$25198 \square (25198 + 1)(25198 \square 2 + 3)6 = (634964402)(50399)6 = \\ = (634964402 + 5039)96 = 63496944196$$

Oxirgi raqami 7 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonni o'ziga o'zini ko'paytirish natijasida hosil bo'ladigan sonlarni topishning umumiy formulasi:

$$\overline{a7 \square a7} = a \square (a + 1)4 \square (a + 1)9 \quad (3)$$

Misol uchun: birlar xonasidagi 7 ning kvadratini ushbu formula orqali hisoblaymiz. Bunda, $a=0$ ekanligi ma'lum.

$$a = 0$$

$$7 \square 7 = 49$$

$$a = 0$$

$$0 \square (0 + 1)4 \square (0 + 1)9 = (0)(4)9 = 49$$

O'nlar sinfini misol sifatida tekshirsak:

$$a = 8$$

$$87 \square 87 = 7569$$

$$a = 8$$

$$8 \square (8 + 1)4 \square (8 + 1)9 = (72)(36)9 = (72 + 3)69 = 7569$$

Yuzlar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 26$$

$$267\overline{267} = 71289$$

$$a = 26$$

$$26\overline{(26+1)4(26+1)9} = (702)(10)89 = (702+10)89 = 71289$$

Minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 955$$

$$9557\overline{9557} = 91336249$$

$$a = 955$$

$$955\overline{(955+1)4(955+1)9} = (912980)(3824)9 = \\ = (912980+382)49 = 91336249$$

O'n minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 9458$$

$$94587\overline{94587} = 8946700569$$

$$a = 9458$$

$$9458\overline{(9458+1)4(9458+1)9} = (89463222)(37836)9 = \\ = (89463222+3783)69 = 8946700569$$

Yuz minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 77777$$

$$777777\overline{777777} = 604937061729$$

$$a = 77777$$

$$77777\overline{(77777+1)4(77777+1)9} = (6049339506)(311112)9 = \\ = (6049339506+31111)29 = 604965061729$$

Oxirgi raqami 8 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonni o'ziga o'zini ko'paytirish natijasida hosil bo'ladigan sonlarni topishning umumiy formulasi:

$$\overline{a8\overline{a8}} = a\overline{(a+1)6(a+1)4} \quad (4)$$

Misol uchun: birlar xonasidagi 8 ning kvadratini ushbu formula orqali hisoblaymiz. Bunda, $a=0$ ekanligi ma'lum.

$$a = 0$$

$$8 \square 8 = 64$$

$$a = 0$$

$$0 \square (0 + 1) 6 \square (0 + 1) 4 = (0)(6) 4 = 64$$

O'nlar sinfini misol sifatida tekshirsak:

$$a = 8$$

$$88 \square 88 = 7744$$

$$a = 8$$

$$8 \square (8 + 1) 6 \square (8 + 1) 4 = (72)(54) 4 = (72 + 5) 44 = 7744$$

Yuzlar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 16$$

$$168 \square 168 = 28224$$

$$a = 16$$

$$16 \square (16 + 1) 6 \square (16 + 1) 4 = (272)(102) 4 = (272 + 10) 24 = 28224$$

$$a = 595$$

$$5958 \square 5958 = 35497764$$

Minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 595$$

$$595 \square (595 + 1) 6 \square (595 + 1) 4 = (354620)(3576) 4 = (354620 + 357) 64 = 35497764$$

O'n minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 9258$$

$$92588 \square 92588 = 8572537744$$

$$a = 9258$$

$$9258 \square (9258 + 1) 6 \square (9258 + 1) 4 = (85719822)(55554) 4 = (85719822 + 5555) 44 = 8572537744$$

Yuz minglar sinfini tekshirsak:

$$a = 88888$$

$$888888 \square 888888 = 790121876544$$

$$a = 88888$$

$$88888 \square (88888 + 1)6 \square (88888 + 1)4 = (7901165432)(533334)4 = \\ = (7901165432 + 53333)44 = 790121876544$$

Yuqorida olingan natijalardan ushbu hulosaga kelshimiz mumkin:

1) Oxirgi raqami 6 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonning kvadratini hisoblash uchun:

$$\overline{a6 \square a6} = a \square (a + 1)(2 \square a + 3)6$$

2) Oxirgi raqami 7 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonning kvadratini hisoblash uchun:

$$\overline{a7 \square a7} = a \square (a + 1)4 \square (a + 1)9$$

3) Oxirgi raqami 8 bilan tugaydigan har qanday sonning kvadratini hisoblash uchun:

$$\overline{a8 \square a8} = a \square (a + 1)6 \square (a + 1)4$$

formulalaridan foydalanishimiz mumkin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

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